

Response of irrigated rice to the application of poultry manure and inorganic fertilizers N, P, and K in Karnataka, India

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The integrated use of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers is important to sustain a higher level of soil fertility and productivity. Poultry manure is a rich source of nutrients and is available in abundant quantity near poultry farms. It has not been fully exploited as a source of organic manure. Hence, we studied the response of rice to poultry manure and NPK under irrigated conditions. The poultry manure used in this experiment contained 3.03% N, 2.6% P, and 1.4% K.

The field experiment was conducted during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons (Aug-Dec). The soil has pH 8.2, 260 kg available N, 42 kg available P, and 650 kg available K ha⁻¹. The available N, P, and K were estimated by the Kjeldahl, Olsen's, and flame photometer method, respectively. The experiment was a split plot conducted at ARS with poultry manure in the main plot and NPK levels in the subplot, replicated thrice. The agronomic efficiency of N (AEN) was calculated by taking the ratio of rice yield to total N applied (Venugopalan and Prasad 1992).

Thirty-day-old seedlings of genotype SIRI-429 were transplanted during the first week of August in 16-m² plots with 20 × 10-cm spacing. A basal dose of 50% N and a full dose of P and K were applied at transplanting and the remaining 50% N was applied in two equal splits at 30-d intervals. The fertilizer dose was applied per treatment.

Grain yield increased with each increment of poultry manure application and was maximum at 3 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure during both years (see table). This was 26% and 19% higher than that of the control during 1998 and 1999, respectively. The significant increase was observed up to 2 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure. Data showed that 1 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure was on a par with 7 t ha⁻¹ of farmyard manure. With the increasing application of poultry manure, AEN decreased. The highest AEN was observed when no organic manure was applied; the lowest was at 4 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure.

Increasing the fertilizer level from 75:35.5:37.5 to 150:75:75 kg NPK ha⁻¹ increased grain yield significantly during both years (see table). The AEN was inversely related. AEN at 75% NPK (112.5:56.3:56.3 kg NPK ha⁻¹) was equivalent to 2 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure.

The interactive effect between poultry manure and inorganic fertilizer was not signifi-

cant. However, data showed that an increase in poultry manure and fertilizer increased rice seed yield. This is true up to 3 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure. At 4 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure, a yield increase was noted only up to 75% NPK. Further increases in NPK did not improve yields. This clearly indicates that, at high poultry manure application rates, 75% NPK was optimum. The AEN decreased with an increased application of poultry manure and fertilizer. However, at 4 t ha⁻¹ of poultry manure, agronomic efficiency did not vary with an increase in NPK. The AEN with farmyard manure (7 t ha⁻¹) was almost equivalent to poultry manure application at 1 t ha⁻¹.

Reference

- Venugopalan MV, Prasad R. 1992. Relative efficiency of ammonium polyphosphate and conventional orthophosphate for wheat and wheat-fodder cowpea cropping sequence. *Indian J. Agron.* 37(2):226-230.

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Effect of manure application and fertilizers N, P, and K application on grain yield and agronomic N efficiency.^a

Application	Treatment						1998 WS		1999 WS	
	Manure			Inorganic			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	AEN
	N	P	K	N	P	K				
	(kg ha ⁻¹)			(kg ha ⁻¹)						
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.6 ± 0.5	48.1	3.6 ± 0.3	48.0
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	112.5	56.3	56.3	3.6 ± 0.1	31.8	4.0 ± 0.6	35.6
0 t M ha ⁻¹	0	0	0	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.0 ± 0.4	26.9	5.3 ± 0.3	53.1
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.5 ± 33.7	33.7	3.8 ± 0.2	36.0
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	112.5	56.3	56.3	3.4 ± 0.1	23.6	4.7 ± 0.5	33.1
1 t PM ha ⁻¹	30	26	14	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.6 ± 0.7	25.6	5.4 ± 0.6	30.2
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.9 ± 0.3	28.7	4.6 ± 0.2	34.5
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.4 ± 0.6	25.6	5.0 ± 0.1	28.7
2 t PM ha ⁻¹	60	52	28	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.8 ± 0.2	23.1	5.4 ± 0.4	26.0
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	75.0	37.5	37.5	4.2 ± 0.4	25.3	4.6 ± 0.1	27.7
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.8 ± 0.1	23.9	4.9 ± 0.1	24.3
3 t PM ha ⁻¹	90	78	42	150.0	75.0	75.0	5.1 ± 0.1	21.4	5.9 ± 0.0	24.4
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	75.0	37.5	37.5	4.1 ± 0.2	21.2	4.3 ± 0.3	21.9
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.8 ± 0.3	20.5	5.3 ± 0.4	22.7
4 t PM ha ⁻¹	120	104	56	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.7 ± 0.7	17.3	5.8 ± 0.2	21.4
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	75.0	37.5	37.5	3.9 ± 0.1	35.5	4.1 ± 0.6	38.7
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	112.5	56.3	56.3	4.3 ± 0.3	29.1	5.1 ± 0.2	34.9
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹	35	10.5	35	150.0	75.0	75.0	4.2 ± 0.6	22.7	5.3 ± 0.3	28.8
Treatment means										
0 t M ha ⁻¹							3.7 ± 0.2 a*	35.6	4.3 ± 0.7 a*	39.6
1 t M ha ⁻¹							3.8 ± 0.6 ab	27.6	4.6 ± 0.7 ab	33.1
2 t M ha ⁻¹							4.4 ± 0.4 bcd	25.8	5.0 ± 0.3 bc	29.7
3 t M ha ⁻¹							4.7 ± 0.4 d	23.5	5.1 ± 0.5 c	25.5
4 t M ha ⁻¹							4.6 ± 0.3 cd	19.7	5.1 ± 0.6 c	22.0
7 t FYM ha ⁻¹							4.1 ± 0.2 abc	29.1	4.8 ± 0.6 b	34.1
	75.0	37.5	37.5	NPK			3.9 ± 0.2 a	32.1	4.2 ± 0.4 a	34.5
	112.5	56.3	56.3	NPK			4.2 ± 0.6 b	25.7	4.8 ± 0.4 b	29.9
	150.0	75.0	75.0	NPK			4.6 ± 0.2 c	22.8	5.5 ± 0.2 c	26.1
Interaction										
Manure × NPK							ns		ns	

^aM = manure, WS = wet season, PM = poultry manure, FYM = farmyard manure, AEN = agronomic N efficiency.

* = significant at 0.05%, ns = not significant.

Adenine, adenosine monophosphate, and cytokinin: nutrients for rice seedling growth in the summer crop season

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Adenine, adenosine monophosphate (AMP), and cytokinin (isopentenyl adenine [IPA], transzeatin [t-Z], and dihydrozeatin [DHZ]) were tested to determine whether they could promote seedling growth of rice variety Tai-Keng 3 in Taiwan. Adenine and AMP are precursors of the

biosynthesis of ATP, nucleic acids, coenzyme A, FAD NAD⁺, and cytokinin. Cytokinin is an inducer of protein synthesis and cell division. Rice seeds were surface-sterilized with 10% NaOCl for 10 min, rinsed with distilled water a few times, and placed under white fluorescent lamps (20 μmol

m⁻² s⁻¹) for germination at 26 °C. Distilled water was replaced daily. Five-day-old germinating seeds were transferred to culture solutions, which included Hoagland solution [Ca(NO₃)₂, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KNO₃, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; MgSO₄, 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KH₂PO₄, 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; Fe-